

PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL ABILITIES OF STUDENTS IN THE MULTIMEDIA MEDIUM

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Annotation: this article reflects on the possibilities of pedagogical conditions in education for the formation of musical abilities of young students in multimedia.

Keywords: educational system, Music Culture, multimedia tools, pedagogical technology, computer.

INTRODUCTION.

It will not be an exaggeration to say that the reforms implemented in our country in recent years, in particular new changes in the field of education, are aimed at the development of our state, the well-being of the people, the upbringing of the younger generation. The importance of education in human education, education is very great. We must not forget that raising a harmonious generation, bringing them to adulthood in every possible way, is one of the main tasks of education, from the reasoning that "modernizing our country and building a strong civil society are our priority goals", as the president noted in his lecture. For this reason, the contribution and influence of the so-called School of the great Dargah in the development of Man and society cannot be compared with anything with the work of teachers and mentors who will decide the future of not only our youth, but our entire people. Today, due to a new approach to each area, the introduction of innovative techniques and technologies, the educational sphere also requires a special modern approach. It is not for nothing that the 21st century is called the age of technology and technology. It is also known to everyone that a special innovative approach to education in the process of globalization, in which science, technology are developing, gives a high result in the quality and effectiveness of Education. The further development of the modern educational and educational process is also strengthened in a number of laws and legislative acts adopted in our country.

Speaking about the development of musical art today and tomorrow, it is permissible to dwell on the meaning and content of the phrase "national music" with special attention. Protecting it from any negative influences, including the influence of alien currents in the spirit of "mass culture", should be one of the goals of ours, which today has set itself before teachers of music culture. When we talk about this, it is worth noting such a situation that the zero young generation must realize in the educational process how invaluable and high their spiritual and cultural values, the art of National Music are. The "works" that some young performers and creative groups present to public attention do not meet any requirements and criteria of art. They are not only music, theme of the work and methods of execution, but also openly foreign in stage movements "pop-art"¹ the fact that imitation of the appearance of The Chi is often found in cases of "stardom patient" without offending true art lovers qolmaydi. So'

¹ "Pop-art"- the public opposition of the (public art)Chi is that they honor objects and objects rather than human beings. domestic consumerism emotions are appreciated. Wikipedia-2022

such actions of young people who try to be known through various clips by distorting and pronouncing them are nothing more than ignorance and a lack of understanding of the true nature of art I think.

In order to prevent and put an end to such problems, cultural organizations, first of all musicologist scientists, master artists, composers, journalists and writers, a large number of art lovers openly express their opinion and direct our youth to proper education, are both debt and a hypothesis to the state and society. It is not for nothing that a person's ear, accustomed to light-yellow, shallow tones, as a result of which his artistic taste, musical culture and thinking are reduced, his spiritual world is occupied by false concepts. Ultimately, it will be difficult for such a person to accept both the unique masterpieces of our national music, such as "Munojot", "Shashmakom", and the works of great composers recognized by the world, such as Beethoven, Mozart, Bach and Tchaikovsky. To prevent such situations, the formation of a healthy creative environment among artists creates the necessary conditions for raising the spiritual world and cultural level of the growing younger generation, to widely enjoy the samples of national and Jakhan music culture of our youth, and on this basis, to further develop musical education, to further improve the personnel training system in this regard,

Literature analysis (review).

"Music" textbooks designed for the school program provide all the tasks intended for students. G. Sharipova, Z. Khodjayeva's "methodology for teaching music" highlights the teacher's methods of working with students in the educational process, approaches to each topic covered with new and specific pedagogical technologies. D.A. Karimova, Sh.A. Yakubova in the book "working on children's musical works" provides information about knowing how to perform works of different shapes and genres, revealing the artistic images of a musical work based on the text of a note, movements of melody, timbre, rhythm, sound, dynamic tones, melody-appropriate posture. E.K. In the "school repertoire" of Djalilov, educational methods, pedagogical, psychological methodological recommendations to the music teacher, feedback on new pedagogical technologies and methodological recommendations were given. G.M. Sharipova, D.F. Asamova, Z.L. Khodjayeva in the "methodology of music teaching theory and school repertoire" practicum we can see that knowledge is given about the use of modern technologies in the preparation of lesson developments, the use of computers, slides, discs, magnetic tapes, the selection and application of methods and methods of teaching music according to the age of each class.

The use of multimedia tools in the educational process is of great importance from a pedagogical - psychological point of view. The material given in it is mastered deeper, the opportunity to save time is achieved, the information received is stored in the memory of a person for a long time, the participation of students of a small school age as passive listeners is reduced, multimedia programs are implemented aimed at improving research and cognitive activity, artistry is introduced into the educational process. In other words, multimedia activates the motivations of education, such as emotional-aesthetic exposure, goal-seeking, research. It is known that the learner remembers only 4/1 of the subject he hears, and only 3/1 of the material he sees; both seeing and hearing contemplates keeps 50% of the information in mind. And when using interactive multimedia technologies, this figure is 75% organizational. Therefore, taking into account the psychophysiological and aesthetic characteristics of thinking and reacting to it, having received a large volume of information, it

is necessary to establish theoretical lessons based on teaching multimedia, that is, multimedia pedagogy. This, in turn, requires a music teacher to have good computer literacy and skills in working with modern techniques, multimedia devices.

Let's take a look at how the simplest of the activities with the participation of computerized, multimedia technologies is created in the course of the lesson. When conducting a lesson in such a way, the teacher will first need a computer, a sound column, a multimedia projector and a plan of the course process, which is carried out using the MS Power Point-97 program, and slides that illuminate them one by one.

A slide (English-slide) refers to a colored or black - and-white photographic image captured on a transparent base, glass plate, or film, showing photostands, video plates in sequence that correspond to a particular subject. Processing of slides is carried out in the MS Power Point program.

- It is advisable to divide the educational materials in the subjects by students into fully meaningful modules, divided into parts in certain stages of the course;

- In order to increase the interest of students in the multimedia application at each stage, it is necessary to use the educational materials of the later stage in special parts of the interest, summarize the text of the work being studied and listened to and reflect in accordance with it;

- In Multimedia applications, educational materials should be distributed and placed in presentation slides in such a way that the presentation of new materials is carried out by repeating educational materials from the previous stage;

- In order to focus on the content of the parts of teaching materials, they can be given together with audio or video tapes (data). Using a multi-window interface to provide (display) images of different views or hypertext gives a good result;

- Multimedia applications can include additional materials, as well as additional materials for deep study of the topic, the formation of the necessary knowledge and skills.

Multimedia applications, the most important elements of which are guidelines or explanations that can provide knowledge. This is the most important didactic education, ensuring the correct understanding of the subject or educational material by students. The pedagogical skills and knowledge of teachers are important here. The presentation of the Multimedia application in the form of references can contain basic concepts, evidence, historical and theoretical materials on the topic, tables of comparison of the characteristics of the elements of Science and other sources of additional information. After studying each part (Songs) of the teaching materials (the slide is displayed, after the teacher's explanation), a summary of the studied teaching materials was expressed in a textual state. In order for other readers to use it, the ability to copy the text of the multimedia application and print it must be available. In the preparation of Multimedia projects, internet resources can be used modern multimedia encyclopedias, electronic textbooks. Over time, the best multimedia applications may appear on the network. Therefore, video presentations, images, graphics, animations, sound music, exercises and finally the teacher's explanations will serve to make the lesson more effective in the future.

When creating a Multimedia application (vision, image, audio, text, music writing, animation, movement, etc.), the connection between the topics of music lessons and external information resources should be in accordance with the purpose of the lesson, find a link. Teaching as much of it as possible by mirroring it in the App, their effective use ensures that

the lessons are fun for the students. Presentation work has an interesting, artistic-emotional effect and makes it exciting. Multimedia tools used in the applications provide a convenient opportunity for students to collaborate with each other, participate in music lessons. Pre-planning these aspects of the educational process is a sign that teachers are responsible

A presentation with good content based on well-planned multimedia applications will undoubtedly attract the attention of students to educational materials, strengthen their desire to acquire, assimilate knowledge. But it should be remembered that paying attention to the use of excess details in the decoration of the appearance (design) of the presentation (applications) can compromise the quality of the lesson. The effectiveness of the presentation decreases if external influences are greatly enhanced in the prepared program. The music teacher should know this and keep in mind when preparing presentation programs. It is necessary to find the balance between the educational material presented in Multimedia applications and the details formed by ko;ra, so that the attention of students is not distracted from the educational matrilines, along with additional details, helps students to study educational materials with interest. Such approaches are useful not only for drawings prepared for music lessons, but also for multimedia presentations in all areas. These aspects of music multimedia applications require the fulfillment of certain requirements in the process of their creation and development².

First of all, it seems to us that when writing a script of multimedia applications, it will be correct to adhere to the following principles. Theoretical rules given on the subject of each lesson, skills to be learned, audio recordings, recordings of melodies to be learned, which instruments to play or perform videos, graphic animations of materials related to music lessons, other activities are deepened, integrated, accessible and application-oriented style; in this case, each application consists of a maximum of 20-25 episodic slides, the duration of which (the time spent on the presentation) can be from 3-5 minutes to 15-20 minutes. Providing music-theoretical material, it is necessary to distinguish several parts, a number of aortic arguments, rules and concepts, and repeat and reinforce them from time to time during the game. It is also recommended to follow the instructions below when preparing a multimedia presentation. In the process of using multimedia in music lessons, that is, preparing a multimedia presentation, it is necessary to highlight what it is going about, reflect the rules of the most striking parts of the topic of the lesson, and most importantly take into account the teacher's short and clear explanations on the topic. The knowledge, concepts, phenomena, images in each application must be clear. In applications, the graphic, image, sound, animation, audio, text, theoretical rules of students are given as a continuation of the theme of the corresponding purpose, the first slide, the second slide, the teacher is creative fantasy, the program for obtaining special effects, intellectual abilities must be high.

A well-thought-out and specially prepared multimedia presentation, which is used in the lesson, should focus students' attention on educational material, increasing their interest in acquiring knowledge. At the same time, it should be remembered that depending on the purpose of the musical base of the Presented Application, special effects (filling elements) should be used if in applications such elements exceed the norm, then the effectiveness of the presentation decreases to such an extent that this can negatively affect the quality and content

² Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

of the lesson. The presentation and multimedia educational material used, in the middle of the special elements drawn up in accordance with it, it is necessary to find such a balance that the attention of students should not be distracted from the educational material, the use of multimedia tools, various technologies. Students' in-depth study of teaching materials is focused on their active passionate participation in these activities. Therefore, all work related to multimedia presentation and its musical decoration should be useful not only for the goals and objectives of education, but also for multimedia presentations. Sound and visual effects should not occupy the main and leading position of any bracket and block additional and basic information that should be given. When creating and preparing Multimedia applications, the following aspects should not be ignored. For each module, there is a suitable description form for students (content of image, video and educational materials) and the appropriate name for the module, context, images, background, image, graphics, musical sound, video and other multimedia options, the use of modullr to model the cognitive activity of students in the process of studying relevant educational materials and create it from its results (for example,; strengthening the knowledge and skills acquired with the help of multimedia tools and restoring communication with students (problems, control tasks, modeling tasks, development of a method for analyzing answers, corrections to incorrect answers, instructions, tips and design assistance). Creating a context suitable for the content of presentation applications, selecting and developing a sequence of images, drawings, tables, diagrams, video images, modulating each section of lessons (applications) from the point of view of effectiveness; it is recommended to compose each module in the following order:

Text of psychological preparation, modular annotation and introduction to it.

- *Educational purpose and objectives of the module;*
- *Multimedia learning materials (applications on the topic);*
- *List of main tasks, mommos, main tasks related to the module;*
- *Examples of pre-created presentations, slides, applications;*
- *New apps and tutorials;*
- *Questions (including answers, comments, recommendations) that identify self-examination and students' taasurots.*
- *List of educational literature on the module, information on the topic of the module (lesson), links to resources on the internet.*

We use Multimedia presentations at such a time:

When creating multimedia presentations for music lessons, it is necessary to take into account the capabilities of the computer, the main features of receiving information from the computer screen. It is necessary to collect information for each lesson on one topic and maintain a single method of its presentation. On the basis of a single goal, it is necessary to strive to harmonize the structure and shape of the provision of educational materials (user interface, use of graphic elements, creation of lesson templates). Currently, it is more convenient to use standard fonts for presentations, such as Times, Arreal. Two or three different fonts and text characters (markers) can be used for the entire presentation and are convenient.

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